

CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPRESSION FAILURE OF CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATED COMPOSITE

Tian Xiang Mao ¹ and Vijay Gupta ²

¹ *Institute of Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100080, China*

² *Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering Department, UCLA*

SUMMARY: An experimental investigation of the failure of selected compression-loaded $[0^\circ]_{48}$, $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$, $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$, $[90^\circ]_{48}$ Graphite/Epoxy composite laminates is described. For comparison with $[\pm \theta^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens, the compression test for specimens of $[30^\circ]_{48}$, $[45^\circ]_{48}$ and $[60^\circ]_{48}$ were also carried out. A simple compressive test technique is used to obtain the experimental data. The experiment results include compressive strength data and description of laminate failure modes and failure mechanisms. The dominant compression failure modes for the laminates in this study were found to be interlaminar shearing (for $[0^\circ]_{48}$, $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens), fiber scissoring (for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimen), in-plane matrix shearing and matrix compression (for $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$, $[90^\circ]_{48}$ specimens). Both $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ and $[30^\circ]_{48}$ specimens had almost the same failure load with the same failure mode, in-plane matrix shearing. The crack was along the fiber direction and the fracture surface was flat in the through-thickness direction. Both $[60^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens had similar failure load and the same failure mode of matrix compression. Both $[45^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens behaved identically until the elastic limit of 150 MPa, after that they behaved quite different.

KEYWORDS : Composite Laminate, Compression Failure, Interlaminar, Matrix Compression

INTRODUCTION

Long fiber-polymer matrix composites, such as carbon fiber in an epoxy matrix, possess excellent tensile properties resulting from the high tensile strength of the fibers.

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However, they fail in compression by plastic microbuckling at stresses of only 60% of their tensile strength. In many applications compressive strength is a design limiting feature. Over the past sixteen years significant improvements have been made to the tensile strength, impact resistance and toughness of these composites. Unfortunately, compressive strength has shown little improvement.

In the past decade a lot of research work has been concentrated to the compressive failure of unidirectional composites and significant progress has been achieved (Fleck and Budiansky)[1]. They carried out the elastic and plastic kinking analyses of microbuckling and it is able to account for some of the experimental observations for the compressive failure of unidirectional composites. They also pointed out that more detailed modeling of damage development in the off-axis plies is required, since the measured toughness G associated with delamination and splitting is more than two orders of magnitude greater than the dissipation due to microbuckling per unit area advance of the microbuckle.

Recently, extensive research work has been conducted in Professor Gupta's group on the compressive failure mechanism for various materials system under both unidirectional and bi-axial compression. Gupta and Anand [2] and Gupta and Grape [3] described the failure mechanisms of the laminated carbon-carbon composites and two dimensional woven carbon/ polyimide laminates under unidirectional and bi-axial compression. They also conducted experimental and analytical investigation of 45° off-axis compression. Shuart and his colleague investigated the compression failure of multidirectional composite laminates [4,5].

In this paper we described the failure mechanism of selected compression - loaded multidirectional composite laminated specimen, such as $[0^\circ]_{48}$, $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$, $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$, $[90^\circ]_{48}$ specimen. Experimental results are presented for graphite-epoxy specimens. The specimens were tested using a simple compression test technique. The experimental results include compressive strength data and descriptions of laminate failure modes and failure mechanisms. The dominant compression failure modes for the laminates in this study were found to be interlaminar shearing, in-plane shearing and fiber scissoring and matrix compression.

SPECIMENS, APPARATUS AND TESTS

The graphite-epoxy composite specimens tested in this investigation were fabricated from commercially available unidirectional Hercules AS4 graphite fiber tapes preimpregnated with 450-K cure Hercules 3502 thermosetting epoxy resin. The tapes were laid to form 48-ply laminates approximately 6 mm thick. The laminates were cured with a computer controlled hot pressing machine in UCLA's composite manufacturing lab using the manufacturer's recommended procedure. All specimens were 25 mm long and 13 mm wide. The loaded ends of each specimen were machined flat and parallel to permit uniform compressive loading. The laminate stacking sequences are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Failure data for compression-loaded laminates

Stacking sequence	Failure Stress MPa
$[0^\circ]_{48}$	968
$[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$	269
$[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$	181
$[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$	247
$[90^\circ]_{48}$	194
$[30^\circ]_{48}$	263
$[45^\circ]_{48}$	240
$[60^\circ]_{48}$	228

The specimens were loaded to failure in axial compression using an Instron 8501 and MTS 8100 testing system, both of them are 100 KN capacity hydraulic testing machine. The specimens were tested to failure by slowly applying a compressive load to simulate a static loading condition. During test the load and displacement of the cross head was automatically recorded by computer and the stress--strain curve can be deduced from these data. For some specimen the microscope was used to observe to cracks at the sides of the specimen during the test. Afterwards the fracture surface has been examined by SEM.

The test specimens and fixtures used in this study are simple and compact. The present compressive test method uses a specimen that is sized to be thick enough to avoid global buckling, and is adequate for providing a good distribution of the flows inherent in the microstructure. The limited specimen size also allowed generation of a reasonable set of data from a single composite panel, without the added panel-to-panel variability resulting

Fig. 1 Specimen (all dimension in mm)

from manufacturing. A schematic of the specimen showing the orientation of fibers and loading direction is shown in Fig. 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results including stress - strain curves and tabulated data are described in this section. The failure stress and strain data are given in Table 1. Failure strain is calculated using laminate end- shortening. Failure load for all laminates except the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ laminates correspond to a catastrophic event that terminates the load-carrying capability of the laminates. Failure load for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ laminates correspond to the near-zero slope of stress-strain curve. Stress-strain data for specimens having similar failure modes are presented together, and these failure modes are described. The experimental results are compared with previous results. [6]

The experimental stress-strain curves for all specimens tested in this study , $[\pm 0^\circ]_{48}$, $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$, $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$, $[90^\circ]_{48}$ are shown in Fig. 2. Typical stress-strain data for $[0^\circ]_{48}$ specimens are shown in Fig. 3. These data are nearly linear to failure, and these specimens have the highest strength of all specimens tested. The dominant failure mode for this group is the interlaminar shearing. The interlaminar shearing failure mode is characterized by brooming and interlaminar cracking. Upon a closer look at the samples, the $[0^\circ]_{48}$ samples fail by plastic kinking.

Fig. 2 Stress-strain curve for all specimen

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curve for $[0^\circ]_{48}$ specimen

Typical stress-strain data for $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens are shown in fig. 4. The degree of nonlinearity for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens is much higher than $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens, and the failure strain for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens is higher than any specimens tested in this investigation. The dominate failure mode for $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens is in-plane matrix shearing. In-plane matrix shearing in angle-ply laminates is characterized by failure surfaces that are parallel to the fiber direction. The failure mode for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens is the combination of in-plane matrix shearing and fiber scissoring.

Fig. 4 Stress-strain curve for $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimen

The specimens showed a linear stress-strain curve with no damage whatsoever on the composite surface prior to 150 MPa. Then there is a strong nonlinearity on stress-strain curve afterwards. At the peak load about 180 MPa, two sets of transverse cracks, appearing as “shadow lines” to the naked eye, were observed on the specimens lateral face ABCD and EFGH (fig. 5). Upon closer examination, it is found that each shadow line on the upper half of the face ABCD has its counterpart on the lower half of the face EFGH, with each representing the two ends of a “scissoring fiber” emerging at the lateral

Fig. 5 Schematic show of the cracks on the sides of $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimen

surfaces. A SEM picture of one of the lateral surface is shown with cracks seen as white lines. During the compression, it was found that the specimen swelled in the middle part and the cracks were not found in the middle section of IJKL. On the other hand, on the outer layer of the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimen, in-plane matrix shearing was found with a crack along the fiber direction.

Typical stress-strain data for $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$ and $[90^\circ]_{48}$ specimens are shown in Fig. 6. The data are very nonlinear, and these specimen have the highest failure strains for all the specimens tested except those of $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$. The dominant failure mode for this group of specimens is matrix compression. The matrix compression failure made is characterized by

a failure surface that extends through the laminate thickness and is oriented at 45 degrees to the middle surface.

Fig. 6 Stress--strain curve for $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$ and $[90^\circ]_{48}$ specimens

For comparison with $[\pm \theta^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens, the compression test for specimens of $[30^\circ]_{48}$, $[45^\circ]_{48}$ and $[60^\circ]_{48}$ were also carried out. The stress-strain curves for specimen $[30^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ are shown in Fig. 7. Both specimens had almost the same failure load with the same failure mode, in-plane matrix shearing. The crack was along the fiber direction and the fracture surface was flat in the through-thickness direction.

Fig. 7 Stress-strain curve for $[30^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens

Fig. 8 Stress-strain curve for $[60^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens

The stress-strain curves for specimen $[60^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$ are shown in Fig. 8. Both specimens had similar failure load and the same failure mode of matrix compression.

Fig. 9 Stress--strain curve for $[45^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens

The stress-strain curves for specimen $[45^\circ]_{48}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ are shown in fig. 9. It is interesting to notice that both of the specimens behaved identically until the elastic limit of 150 MPa. After that they behaved quite different. The failure mode for $[45^\circ]_{48}$ specimen

is the combination of in-plane matrix shearing and the matrix compression failure. The fracture surface is parallel to the fiber direction, but not flat in through-the-thickness direction just like the failure of matrix compression mode making a 45 degree angle with the middle plane. The failure mode for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens is the combination of fiber-scissoring and in-plane matrix shearing. Fig. 10 shows the schematic view of the fiber scissoring. Under compression loading, the 45 degree fiber bundles in the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens tend to scissor clockwise and the -45 degree fiber bundles tend to scissor counter-clockwise. On the left hand side lateral surface of the specimen, the lower parts of the 45 degree fiber bundles moved out from the surface and parts of the -45 degree fiber bundles moved in from the surface. Both ends of the specimen attached with the loading fixture can't move because of friction, so the middle parts of the specimen swell. The most important evidence for fiber scissoring is that no cracks developed on the middle section of the specimen face IJKL.

Fig. 10

CONCLUSION

This paper describes the failure of selected compression loaded multidirectional Graphite/Epoxy composite laminates. Experimental results for the $[\pm\theta^\circ]_{12s}$ -class laminates are presented and include failure stress, failure strain and laminate failure modes. For comparison, selected compression results for $[\theta^\circ]_{48}$ specimens are also presented. Plastic kinking failure and interlaminar shearing are dominate failure modes for $[0^\circ]_{48}$ specimens, in-plane matrix shearing is the failure made for $[\pm 30^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens, in-plane matrix shearing and fiber scissoring are the failure modes for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{12s}$ specimens, and matrix compression is the failure mode for $[\pm 60^\circ]_{12s}$, $[90^\circ]_{48}$ specimens.

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